

118 YEARS OF PASTEUR INSTITUTE NIŠ
118 ГОДИНА ПАСТЕРОВОГ ЗАВОДА У НИШУ

52 Days of Preventive Medicine

International Congress

52. Дани превентивне медицине
међународни конгрес

25-28. September 2018.
Niš, Serbia

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS ЗБОРНИК РЕЗИМЕА

Endorsed by:
У организацији:

Public Health Institute Niš
Институт за јавно здравље Ниш

Faculty of Medicine,
University of Niš
Медицински факултет
Универзитета у Нишу

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PUBLIC HEALTH INSTITUTE NIŠ
ИНСТИТУТ ЗА ЈАВНО ЗДРАВЉЕ НИШ

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SERBIAN MEDICAL SOCIETY OF NIŠ
СРПСКО ЛЕКАРСКО ДРУШТВО ПОДРУЖНИЦА НИШ

52nd DAYS OF PREVENTIVE MEDICINE
52. ДАНИ ПРЕВЕНТИВНЕ МЕДИЦИНЕ

INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS
МЕЂУНАРОДНИ КОНГРЕС

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS
ЗБОРНИК РЕЗИМЕА

НИШ, 2018.

Editor in Chief

Уредник
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Technical Editor

Техничкиуредник
dipl. ing. Stefan Bogdanović

Publisher

Издавач
Public Health Institute Niš – Институт за јавно здравље Ниш
Faculty of Medicine Niš, University of Niš – Медицински факултет у Нишу, Универзитет у Нишу
Serbian Medical Society of Niš – Српско лекарско друштво подружница Ниш

For publisher

За издавача
Prof. dr Miodrag Stojanović

Printed in

Штампарија и место штампања
Галаксија, Ниш, Србија

Number of copies

Тираж
350

Under the patronage of

Под покровитељством

Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia

Министарства просвете, науке и технолошког развоја Републике Србије

Ministry of Health of the Republic of Serbia

Министарства здравља Републике Србије

All abstracts are published in the book of abstracts in the form in which they were submitted by the authors, who are responsible for their content.
Сви сажетци су публиковани у зборнику резимеа у облику у коме су достављени од стране аутора, који су одговорни за њихов садржај.

The content of this publication is available online at dpm.izjz-nis.org.rs
Садржај ове публикације је доступан на Интернет адреси dpm.izjz-nis.org.rs

Dr Stanko Marjanović is participating in realisation of the Museum of Health Culture exposition.

У реализацији изложбе у Музеју здравствене културе учествује др Станко Марјановић.

The continuing education program number A-1-1253/18 was accredited by the decision of the Health Council of the Republic of Serbia No. 153-02-1550/2018-01 from 21. 05. 2018.

Програм континуиране едукације је под бројем А-1-1253/18 акредитован одлуком Здравственог савета Републике Србије број: 153-02-1550/2018-01 од 21. 05. 2018. године.

ISBN 978-86-915991-9-5

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CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији - Народна библиотека Србије, Београд

614.4(048)

616-084(048)

INTERNATIONAL Congress Days of Preventive Medicine (52; 2018; Niš)
Book of Abstracts - Зборник резимеа / 52nd Days of Preventive Medicine, International
Congress [25-28. September 2018. Niš] - 52. Дани превентивне медицине,
међународни конгрес; [endorsed by] Public Health Institute Niš [and] Faculty of
Medicine Niš [and] Serbian Medical Society of Niš - [у организацији] Институт за
јавно здравље Ниш [и] Медицински факултет Ниш [и] Српско лекарско друштво
подружница Ниш; [editor in chief, уредник Biljana Kosić]. – Niš : Public Health
Institute : Faculty of Medicine : Serbian Medical Society, 2018 (Ниш : Галаксија). - 240
str. : ilustr. ; 30 cm

Tiraž 350. - Bibliografija uz pojedine apstrakte.

ISBN 978-86-915991-9-5 (PHI)

1. Public Health Institute (Niš) 2. Faculty of Medicine (Niš) 3. Serbian
Medical Society (Niš)

а) Превентивна медицина - Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 268784396

6. THE AVAILABILITY OF TOBACCO, ALCOHOL AND ILLICIT DRUGS TO THE SIXTEEN YEARS AGED PUPILS IN THE CITY OF NOVI SAD

Snežana Ukropina^{1,2}, Mijatović Jovanović V^{1,2}., Ivana Radić I^{1,2}., Dušan Čanković D^{1,2}., Čanković S.,^{1,2} Nićiforović Šurković O^{1,2}., Tomašević T^{1,2}.

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Objective: Determination of availability of tobacco, alcohol and illegal drugs to the sixteen years aged pupils in the City of Novi Sad, according to their gender, school success and level of parental control.

Materials and methods: Survey applied *ESPAD* questionnaire on availability of tobacco, alcohol and illicit drugs, among 480 male and 587 female pupils, aged sixteen years.

Results:

Females were more often stating tobacco as easily available (85.6%) ($p < 0.05$). All alcoholic beverages were easily available at both genders but larger availability has been stated for beer by females compared to males (86.9% vs 84.5%; $p < 0.05$) and young whose parents are not aware where their children are spending Saturday evening (93.3%) compared to others (84.9%; $p < 0.05$). Larger availability of alcopops (74.8%) was asserted by young of excellent or very good school success ($p < 0.05$). Larger availability of strong alcoholic drinks was determined at young whose parents has lower level of parental control (83.9% vs. 69.1%; $p < 0.05$). Wine has been available in 79.0% cases. Marijuana has been determined as the most available illegal drug at 50.2% of young, more often at young whose parents had lower control criterion for off-time (33.1% vs. 48.0%; $p < 0.05$). The high estimate of young on availability of amphetamine (25.9%), metamphetamine (26.2%), sedatives (47.2%), ecstasy (35.6%), cocaine (19.6%) and crack (18.4%) was found.

Conclusion: The high estimate on availability of psychoactive substances among sixteen years old pupils in Novi Sad has been determined. It is necessary to increase controlling mechanisms for the application of relevant laws in this field and enhance education of young and their parents.

Key word: Tobacco use, Alcohol use, Illegal drugs abuse, Availability